

Mechatronic design of an underwater multisensor system for optical data acquisition

Alessandro Bucci^{*,†}, Cosimo Fredducci^{*,†}, Gherardo Liverani^{*,†}, Jonathan Gelli^{*,†}, Lorenzo Bartalucci^{*,†},
Francesco Ruscio^{*,†}, Vincenzo Manzari[△], Mirko Stifani[△], Riccardo Costanzi^{*,†}, Alessandro Ridolfi^{*,†}

* Department of Industrial Engineering (DIEF), University of Florence, Via di Santa Marta 3, Florence, Italy

† Interuniversity Center of Integrated Systems for the Marine Environment (ISME)

* Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell'Informazione e Centro di Ricerca "E. Piaggio", Università di Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, Pisa, Italy

△ Centro di Supporto e Sperimentazione Navale (CSSN), Italian Navy, La Spezia, Italy

Abstract—The electromechanical design of a vision system, developed by the ISME nodes of the University of Florence (UNIFI) and the University of Pisa (UNIFI), Italy, is presented. The system is designed to test Visual Odometry algorithms and can be employed as a standalone device or in conjunction with an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV). In this regard, the module presents a wide variety of sensors and is intended to have its power supply. The project constraints are described, and the main features of the prototype are reported.

Index Terms—Data acquisition, underwater system, mechatronic design.

I. INTRODUCTION

The underwater environment represents one of the most challenging scenarios for navigation algorithm development, as global localization sensors, e.g., the Global Positioning System (GPS), cannot be exploited. Exteroceptive sensors capable of perceiving the surrounding environment, such as optical cameras, are necessary to accomplish typical underwater mission tasks, such as seabed inspection, automatic target recognition, and 2D and 3D reconstructions. Considering the high-quality images that the digital cameras can acquire, these devices can be employed as replacement or support to the standard sensors used for navigation purposes, e.g., the Doppler Velocity Log (DVL) [1]. Most of the current vision systems for underwater missions are integrated with a carrier vehicle, which provides power supply, and contains a limited set of sensors [2], [3]. An innovative vision system for underwater missions has been designed to overcome these limitations. The module, named hereafter the Visual Odometry for Inspection Robots (VOIR) module, guarantees power and computational independence, sensor redundancy, and a variable baseline between cameras. The proposed prototype aims to satisfy the previously introduced properties to ensure flexibility and adaptability to different working conditions and to accomplish several tasks. Indeed, the VOIR module can be employed

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not only as a testing platform for monocular, stereo VO and Visual-Inertial Odometry (VIO) algorithms [4], [5], but also as an acquisition system to capture high-definition images for photogrammetry purposes and as a multi-camera system for the automatic detection of object of potential interest.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Regarding the computational requirements, the VOIR module needs to guarantee the capability of acquiring the data from the cameras and all the onboard sensors and processing them in real time. In this regard, the most relevant included sensors are:

- two mono cameras (FCB-ER8550 by SONY);
- one stereo camera (ZED2 by STEREO LABS);
- one Inertial Measurement Unit (Orientus by Advanced Navigation);
- one barometer depth sensor (Bar30 by BlueRobotics);
- one Echo Sounder (852 Ultra-Miniature Echo Sounder by Imagenex).

The ability to both elaborate and process all the data is ensured by the presence on board of two computers: the main computer (PICO-WHU4 with 8th generation i7 processor by AAEON) and a support computer (Raspberry Pi4 with 8GB RAM); while the sensor management is divided between the two computers, the elaboration of the acquired information is left to the main computer. Finally, two LED lights (UWL-400 by Outland Technology) are positioned outside the main body to obtain images even in low light conditions. The main properties of the VOIR module are reported in Table I.

TABLE I
VOIR MODULE MAIN FEATURES.

Features	Value
Dimensions (closed)	1054 x 260 x 210 mm
Dimensions (open)	921 x 538 x 210 mm
Autonomy	3 h (minimum)
Power Supply Voltage	12.8 V
Maximum Operating Depth	150 m (maximum)

The device's power supply comprises eight lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO4) batteries. The power on the module is

Fig. 1. Scheme of the connection between the devices.

distributed and converted to the necessary voltages, mainly by DC-to-DC converters with an output of 3 V, 12 V, and 24 V. The task of managing the recharge process of the batteries is delegated to a Battery Management System (BMS), connected to a dedicated recharge connector (Fig. 1).

An opening and closing system for the camera cases allows the module to be manually placed in a completely open configuration during its operation and to be closed when the module is not used. Because of this, it is possible to determine a reduction in hydrodynamic resistance and even portability and management of the module are more favored. The mechanism has been created with two articulated quadrilateral structures, which allow the mono cameras to be kept parallel to themselves during the opening and closing process and consequently avoid rotation around their axis. The meshing gears, that move together with each quadrangle, guarantee the translational synchronization of the two mono cameras (see Fig. 2). An indexing plunger allows fixing the cameras in four different positions, to which an accurately measured baseline value is associated. This can be useful in the evaluation phase of the stereo VO algorithms to analyze the influence of the baseline value between the two cameras on the trajectory estimation. Neutral buoyancy is fundamental for the whole VOIR module to not interfere with the vehicle buoyancy. The foam, cut to get the desired shape, is positioned over the cylindrical body and around the two spotlights, to guarantee a neutral buoyancy in each possible configuration. Two handles are placed above the center of gravity of the vision module to facilitate transport. Furthermore, considering that the module can operate as a standalone platform, the handles can be used by a diver to carry the module during inspection missions. Finally, on the top of the cylindrical body, a guide permits an easy and fast connection between the module and several torpedo-shaped vehicles.

Fig. 2. Open (top) and closed (bottom) configuration of the VOIR module.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The development and electromechanical design of a testing platform for monocular, stereo VO, and VIO algorithms have been proposed. The VOIR module has been introduced, firstly analyzing the need to develop new vision-based algorithms, then proceeding with the description of mechanical design and electronic components. The main field of application of the VOIR module is vision-based algorithms testing, and it can be used either in conjunction with an AUV or as a standalone device carried by a diver. Regarding future works, the VOIR module will be employed for optical data gathering during test campaigns in conjunction with an AUV and as a standalone system and visual odometry algorithms will be tested to evaluate their performances.

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